

ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT OF MANGO REJUVENATION TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPED BY DR. BALASAHEB SAWANT KONKAN KRISHI VIDYAPEETH, DAPOLI ON FARM ECONOMY OF KONKAN REGION (M.S.)

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MS Received: 07.09.2025; MS Revised:03.10.2025; MS Accepted:04.10.2025)

MS 34589

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURAL ECONOMICS)

Abstract:

In the present study, partial budget technique was used for the evaluating impact of the mango rejuvenation technologies developed by Dr. Balasaheb Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli. The technologies considered for impact analysis were mango rejuvenation techniques used in mango orchard and the adaptation of Alphonso mango variety in the Konkan region of Maharashtra. for this purpose, data collected from the pertaining year 2023-24. The per hectare total additional cost and additional returns incurred due to adoption of mango rejuvenation techniques in Konkan region was found ₹ 9,105 and ₹ 61,801, respectively. Whereas, in case of adoption of Alphonso variety over another local variety the total additional cost and additional returns incurred was ₹ 67270 and ₹ 1,73,825. Thus, the total economic worthiness of the adoption of mango rejuvenation techniques in mango orchard was ₹ 52,696 per hectare. Whereas, total economic worthiness of the university released Alphonso mango variety over other competing local varieties was ₹ 106,555 per hectare.

Keywords: Additional cost, Alphonso, Mango, Partial Budget, Rejuvenation Techniques, Economic impact

Introduction:

India is the largest producer of mango in the world (43.3 lakh tonnes) and ranks first in area and production. The total production of mango in India is 18.431 MT from about 2.516 million ha area with the productivity of 7.3 MT ha⁻¹ (Anon. 2015b). India contributes about 64 % of the world mango production. According to the APEDA, in the year 2024-25 India exported 26667.24 tonnes of mangoes worth Rs. 413.48 crores. In Maharashtra, mango is occupying an area of 4.82 lakh ha with annual production of 6.33 MT with productivity of 1.3 MT ha⁻¹ (Anon. 2015b). In Konkan, 1.23 lakh ha productive area was under mango cultivation having annual production of 2.41 lakh MT. The productivity of mango in Konkan is about 2.5 to 3.0 MT ha⁻¹. India, holds only a 5.20% share in global mango exports. The cumulative investment in mango to date amount to 241.16 million rupees. In Konkan. Dr. B. S. Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli, since its establishment in 1972, have been carrying out all round, multidisciplinary research on various aspects of mango. The research focus of the university is concentrated mainly on rice and horticultural crops. Among the horticultural crops, maximum research efforts have been concentrated on mango, cashew, and coconut, which are major horticultural crops of the region. This has resulted in development and release of seven varieties of mango namely Ratna, Sindhu, Konkan Ruchi, Alphonso, Suvarna, Konkan Raja, Konkan Samrat etc. Among this seven varieties Alphonso is world famous mango variety. It is widely used in Konkan region and it is also awarded with Geographical Indication (GI) Tag. Dr. Balasaheb Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli is one of the (out of four) applicants for this GI tag. Other varieties such as Ratna, Sindhu, Konkan Ruchi etc. are also popular and used for specific purposes. Moreover, the university have recommended more than 50 Technologies and research recommendations. In this context, it was imperative to examine the impact of mango technology developed by Dr. Balasaheb Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli. The present study therefore has been undertaken to quantify impact of university released Alphonso variety and impact of rejuvenation technique in mango orchard on farm economy in the state in general and in the Konkan in particular.

Methodology

The Konkan region of Maharashtra state was selected purposively for this study, looking at the agro-climatic suitability of the region for the mango plantation. In the Konkan region, Sindhudurg, Ratnagiri, Raigad, and (Thane + Palghar) districts are leading in the area, production of mango, and hence selected purposively for the present

study. Three tahsils, from each district, were selected based on maximum area under mango crop. Two villages from each selected tahsils were selected randomly. From each selected village, 5 mango farmers were selected randomly. Thus, the final sample consisted of four districts, twelve tahsils, twenty-four villages, and 120 mango farmers. The primary data for the present study pertained for agriculture year 2023-24

Analytical Tools:

Partial budgeting

The economic viability of partial change in the farm such as use of new variety or new technology or new innovation or new practice or new equipment or new service can be assessed by using the partial budget approach. In the present study partial budget approach was used for estimating the economic impact of mango technologies developed by Dr. Balasaheb Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli.

Partial budgeting is a method of organizing information about the cost and benefits from some change in the technologies being used on the farm. The aim is to estimate the change that will occur in farm profit or loss from some change in the farm plan. Partial budgets do not calculate the total income and expenses for each of the alternative plan but list only those items of income and expense that change. They measure changes in cost and returns to limited resources.

Partial budget includes four components viz. added cost and reduced income on debit side, and reduced cost and added returns on credit side. Added cost includes additional cost incurred on inputs over the previous technology. Reduced income includes reduction in returns either in yield or monetary terms by adopting new technology over the old. Similarly, reduced cost covers the reduction in cost of input and added returns covers additional income earned from new technology.

Results And Discussion:

Development and release of varieties:

A state Agricultural University viz; Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli has been established for the Konkan region on 18th May 1972. The university was renamed on 12 February 2001 as a Dr. Balasaheb Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli, (DBSKKV, Dapoli). Since its establishment, the research focus of the university is concentrated mainly on rice and horticultural crops including mango, coconut and cashew. This has resulted in development and release of seven varieties of mango. List of mango varieties released by DBSKKV, Dapoli is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Details regarding mango varieties released by Dr. B.S.K.K.V., Dapoli.

Sr. No.	Varieties	Year of release
1	Ratna (Neelum X Alphonso)	1981
2	Sindhu (Ratna X Alphonso)	1992
3	Konkan Ruchi (Neelum X Alphonso)	1999
4	Alphonso (By selection)	2002
5	Suvarna (Alphonso X Neelum)	2009
6	Konkan Raja (Banglora X Himmayuddin)	2010
7	Konkan Samrat (Alphonso X Tommy Atkins)	2014

It is seen from Table 1 that seven mango varieties have been released by Dr. Balasaheb Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, namely Ratna, Sindhu, Konkan Ruchi, Alphonso, Suvarna, Konkan Raja, and Konkan Samrat. Among this seven varieties Alphonso is world famous mango variety. It is widely used in Konkan region and it is also awarded with Geographical Indication (GI) Tag. Dr. Balasaheb Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth, Dapoli is one of the (out of four) applicants for this

GI tag. Other varieties such as Ratna, Sindhu, Konkan Ruchi etc. are also popular and used for specific purposes.

Development of mango technologies:

The university have recommended more than 50 Technologies and research recommendations. However, gist of the mango technologies and recommendations is given in Table 2.

Table 2. Gist of mango production and protection technologies developed by Dr. BSKKV, Dapoli.

Sr. No.	Gist of mango production and protection technologies
1	Paclobutrazol for regular bearing in mango
2	Rejuvenation of old mango orchards
3	High density planting
4	Nutrient management: <i>Amrashakti</i> Multi nutrient spray
5	Spongy tissue management
6	Standardized propagation technique (Epicotyl grafting)
7	Intercropping with vegetables, spices and flower crops
8	Other technology related mango production and protection including irrigation schedule, fertilizer management, insect-pest and disease management and harvesting method and time.

The technologies in mango developed by Dr. Balasaheb Sawant Konkan Krishi Vidyapeeth (Dr. BSKKV), Dapoli have played an important role in enhancing mango production, orchard sustainability, and income stability of mango growers in the Konkan region (Table 2). The technologies address critical constraints related to irregular bearing, low productivity of senile orchards, inefficient input use, and pest-disease incidence. The use of paclobutrazol for regular bearing has helped in mitigating the problem of alternate bearing. Similarly, the rejuvenation of old mango orchards has enabled growers to restore productivity in senile plantations. The high-density planting technique has improved land-use efficiency. Adoption of *Amrashakti* multi-nutrient spray under nutrient management practices has ensured balanced nutrition, resulting in improved flowering, fruit set, and fruit quality. The spongy tissue management technology in Alphonso mango, has reduced post-harvest losses. The standardized epicotyl grafting technique has improved the availability of quality planting material, ensuring uniform orchards and higher survival rates. In addition, intercropping with vegetables, spices, and flower crops has

provided supplementary income during the gestation period of mango orchards. Other production and protection technologies related to irrigation scheduling, fertilizer application, insect-pest and disease management, and harvesting methods have collectively contributed to efficient resource use and to increase yield.

Economic impact of university developed technologies in mango:

Economic Impact of rejuvenation techniques in mango orchards.

Partial budgeting techniques was used to capture the economic impact of the rejuvenation techniques in mango orchards. There were four components in partial budgeting. First, the added cost due to the rejuvenation technique in mango orchard was considered. This includes list of all increased expenses due to rejuvenation techniques adopted in mango orchard over non-rejuvenating orchards. The second component was the reduced returns or income due to rejuvenation technique in mango orchard over non-rejuvenating orchards. The third component was the reduced cost due to the rejuvenation techniques in mango orchard over non-rejuvenating orchards.

Table 3. Economic impact of the rejuvenating techniques in mango orchard in Konkan region.

Sr. No.	Debit side		Sr. No.	Credit side	
A	Added cost per ha	Amount (₹)	C	Reduced cost per ha	Amount (₹)
	i) Human labour	2,815		-	-
	ii) Input cost	6,217		-	-
	iii) Research cost	73		-	-
	Sub total (A)	9,105		Sub total (B)	-
B	Reduced returns per ha		D	Added Returns per ha	
	-	-		Yield	61,801
	Sub total (C)	-		Sub total (D)	61,801
	Total debit	9,105		Total credit	61,801
	Economic impact of rejuvenation techniques in mango orchard over non-rejuvenated mango orchards in Konkan region				52,696

The fourth component was the added returns or income due rejuvenation techniques in mango orchard over non-rejuvenating orchards, due to increase in yield. The final step in the partial budget was the summary indicated by the difference between the credit and the debit.

Debit and credit side of partial budgeting and list of all increased expenses due to the rejuvenation technique in mango orchard over non-rejuvenating mango orchard were presented in the Table 3.

Table 3 revealed that the total additional cost of rejuvenating techniques in mango orchard over non rejuvenating orchard was observed to be ₹ 9105 per hectare. Obviously, the reduced costs were

zero. The added returns due to rejuvenating techniques in mango orchard over non rejuvenating orchard were ₹ 61,801. Obviously, the reduced return per hectare were zero. Thus, the total economic worthiness of the rejuvenating techniques in mango orchard over non rejuvenating mango orchard in the region was ₹ 52,696 per hectare.

The economic impact of university developed Alphonso variety over the local variety in the Konkan region

To capture the economic impact of Alphonso mango variety over the local mango variety, partial budgeting was done and the results of which are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Economic impact of the Alphonso variety in the Konkan region.

Debit side		Credit side	
Sr. No.	Amount (₹)	Sr. No.	Amount (₹)
A	Added cost per ha	C	Reduced cost per ha
	i) Human labour		-
	ii) Input cost		-
	iii) Research cost		-
	Sub total (A)		Sub total (B)
	67270		-
B	Reduced returns per ha	D	Added Returns per ha
	-		Yield
	Sub total (C)		1,73,825
	-		Sub total (D)
	Total debit		1,73,825
	67270		Total credit
			1,73,825
Economic impact of the university released Alphonso variety of mango over local variety of mango in Konkan region			106,555

The Alphonso variety of mango was released in the year 1981. Table 4 revealed that the total additional cost of university released alphonso mango variety over other competing local varieties was observed to be ₹ 67270 per hectare. Obviously, the reduced costs (or saving) were zero. The added returns due to university released alphonso mango variety over other competing local varieties were ₹ 1,73,825. Obviously, the reduced returns per hectare were zero. Thus, the total economic worthiness of the university released alphonso mango variety over other competing local varieties in the Konkan region was ₹ 106,555 per hectare.

Conclusions:

The economic worthiness of the rejuvenation techniques in mango orchard over non rejuvenating mango orchard in the Konkan region was ₹ 52,696 per hectare. Whereas, total economic worthiness of the university released alphonso mango variety over other competing local varieties in the Konkan region was ₹ 106,555 per hectare. It is concluded that the adoption of university-released mango variety Alphonso generated higher income than other local varieties. Whereas, adoption of rejuvenation techniques in mango orchard over non-rejuvenated mango orchards generated higher income per hectare.

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